

The South Atlantic Dipole: Mechanisms, variability and impacts over South America

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Outline of the Presentation

South Atlantic Climate Background

Introducing the South Atlantic Dipole (SAD)

Evolution of Scientific Understanding

Physical Mechanisms

Seasonal Variations and Indices

Impacts on South American Climate

Interactions With Other Climate Modes

Climate Change Effects

Model Representation and Future Projections

Final Remarks

Why studying teleconnections matters

From previous lectures:

- Teleconnections link distant regions.
- Role of the oceans in climate variability
- ENSO, PDO, SAM, IOD, AMO, TAD and affect South America
- What about the South Atlantic Ocean? Is there a variability mode that can influence the climate in the surrounding regions?

Figure 1. Main source regions of the teleconnection patterns included in this study being the El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO), the Pacific Decadal Oscillation (PDO), the Atlantic Multidecadal Oscillation (AMO), the Tropical Atlantic Dipole (TAD), the South Atlantic Dipole (SAD), the Southern Annular Mode (SAM), the Madden–Julian Oscillation (MJO), and the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD).

Reboita et al. (2021)

Let's review the main South Atlantic climatological features

Sea-Level Pressure and Surface Winds

Jan

Sea-Level Pressure and Surface Winds

Jul

And the main South Atlantic oceanic features

- **Benguela Current (BeC)** – cold, flowing northward along the African coast
 - **South Equatorial Current (SEC):** westward flow
 - **Brazil Current (BC)** – warm, flowing southward along the Brazilian coast
- **Malvinas (Falklands) Current (MC):** cold subpolar current flowing northward, meeting the warm Brazil Current near 35°S
- **Brazil–Malvinas Confluence Zone:** region of strong temperature gradients
 - **Subtropical Gyre** transfers heat and momentum
 - **South Atlantic Current (SAC):** toward Africa.

Ksepka and Thomas (2021)

What is the South Atlantic Dipole (SAD)?

(Reboita et al., 2021, and references therein)

- The South Atlantic Dipole (SAD) is the dominant mode of coupled atmosphere–ocean variability over the South Atlantic
- Characterized by a northeast–southwest oriented dipole pattern with centers of action over the tropical and extratropical South Atlantic
- It presents variability on intraseasonal, interannual, and interdecadal timescales

*Correlation between SST anomalies and SVD time coefficients
obtained from the SST indicating the SAD
adapted from Bombardi et al. (2014)*

Why studying the SAD makes us feel so sad sometimes?

- Its investigation still faces many challenges
- Few in-situ observations over the South Atlantic and surrounding countries before the 1980s (onset of the Satellite Era)

The ERA5 global reanalysis from 1940 to 2022

Maps of data counts for the conventional part of the observing system, separating by vicennium (20-year time period, from left to right, except for the last column, which shows observations until December 2022) and by observable (from top to bottom). Numbers indicate the average data counts assimilated per month. White areas indicate no data assimilated.

Fig1 Soci et al. (2024)

Why studying the SAD makes us feel so sad sometimes?

- Known Impacts mainly limited to South America and Africa
- Less attention compared to ENSO or the Indian Ocean Dipole
- Results are dependent on the data, time period, and statistical method used

Yet, beyond these challenges, the SAD offers many opportunities for new research!

So, how has the SAD been discovered and studied over time?

The moment the South Atlantic first caught my eye...

- **2001 energy crisis in Brazil: weak La Niña (Modoki?)**
- **A dipole-like SST pattern appeared in the South Atlantic – SAD?**
- My PhD research tried to link this pattern to the drought
- **But Atmospheric GCM failed to reproduce the continental rainfall response via SASST forcing** → suggesting the **atmosphere might be driving the ocean** (Drumond & Ambrizzi, 2005)
- Since then... South Atlantic never left my mind

*JFM 2001 SST anomalies
Drumond Ambrizzi (2005)*

JFM 2001 Obs precipitation anomalies

SASST experiment precip anomalies

A brief history

Late 1990s–2000s – First Identifications

Venegas et al. (1997): EOF/SVD - coupled SST dipole – MSLP linked to shifts in the South Atlantic Subtropical High

Methodological Challenges

EOF/SVD-based analysis: sensitive to preprocessing choices, domain, and analysis period (Kayano et al., 2013), leading to controversies (Palastanga et al., 2002).

2010s – Concept Consolidation

- Morioka et al. (2011) - dipole as EOF1 (SASD, summer peak)
- Nnamchi et al. (2011) – dipole as EOF2 (SAOD, winter peak).
- Both represent the same physical mode (Nnamchi et al., 2017).
- Later studies (Kayano et al., 2013; **Bombardi et al., 2014**; Bier, 2023) identified dipole as the leading SST-MSLP couple mode (SAD).
- Kayano et al. (2013): additional SAO climate variability modes

Physical Processes

Atmosphere-ocean coupling related with South Atlantic Subtropical High variability

- **Changes in the strength/position of the SASH** modify surface winds and heat fluxes, which influence SST patterns across the basin (Venegas et al., 1997; Morioka et al., 2011; Nnamchi et al. 2011).

Negative SAD phase:

Tropics cooler, extratropics warmer

Basin-wide higher SLP → stronger SASH

Positive SAD phase:

Opposite SST anomaly pattern.

Weaker/shifted SASH

Negative SAD Phase – First SVD SST/SLP - Venegas et al. (1997)

SAD Growth phase (Morioka et al., 2011)

- **Atmospheric driver**
- Southward shift and intensification SASH changes surface winds, affecting evaporation and latent heat flux.
- where winds become stronger - evaporation and latent heat loss increase
- where winds become weaker - evaporation and latent heat loss reduce
- Stronger winds increase turbulence and **deepen the mixed layer**, reducing shortwave heating efficiency → reinforces **negative SST anomalies**.
- Weaker winds reduce turbulence and **shoal the mixed layer**, increasing shortwave heating efficiency → reinforces **positive SST anomalies**

SAD Decay phase (Morioka et al., 2011)

- Seasonal cycle: from summer to late autumn, **mixed layer deepens** as winds strengthen and solar heating weakens.
- Deepening ML → **entrainment of cooler subsurface water**, which damps SST anomalies.
- Late autumn: stronger climatological winds → **increase latent heat loss**, enhancing surface cooling.
- Entrainment + latent flux → **decay of the SAD pattern**.

Physical Processes

- **Nnamchi et al. (2011)** explain the SAD evolution through processes that peak in winter, also showing a ocean–atmosphere coupling.
- **New understanding (Manta et al., 2024)**
 - The SAD is shaped by **both atmospheric and oceanic variability**.
 - Their relative influence changes with **timescale** of oscillations

the SAD is complex, and there is more than one way to interpret its physical drivers.

Seasonal Variants: SASD and SAOD

- The SAD presents seasonal variations (Nnamchi et al., 2017), expressed through two main modes.

- **South Atlantic Subtropical Dipole (SASD)**

Morioka et al. (2011)

- Peaks in austral summer, when SASH shifts southward
- Confined to subtropical latitudes

- **South Atlantic Ocean Dipole (SAOD)**

Nnamchi et al. (2011)

- Peaks in austral winter, when SASH shifts northward
- Extends across broader latitudes

Morioka et al. (2011) 1st SST EOF 1960-2008 (20.4%) HADISST

Nnamchi et al. (2011) 2nd SST EOF 1950-2008

How do we monitor SAD?

- Two main Indices based on SST anomaly difference between two regions
- SAD → NE pole - SW pole
- + SAD → warmer NE pole & cooler SW pole
- Index choice may affect results

South Atlantic Ocean Dipole Index

SAODI – (Nnamchi et al., 2011) red boxes

- NE pole: 10°E–20°W, 0–15°S
- SW pole: 10–40°W, 25–40°S
- It captures equatorial influences.

South Atlantic Subtropical Dipole Index

SASDI – (Morioka et al., 2011) green boxes

- Focuses on subtropical variability
- NE pole: 0–20°W, 15–25°S
- SW pole: 10–30°W, 30–40°S

Important Note

- SAODI's northern pole overlaps the Atlantic Niño region
- SASDI's southern pole is fully inside SAODI's southern domain

Author	SAD	Index Name	Main Season
Morioka et al. 2011	EOF1	SASD	Austral Summer (DJF)
Nmanchi et al. 2011	EOF2	SAOD	Austral Winter (JJA)

Nogueira et al. (2025) in preparation

Strengths and Limitations of SAD Indices

Strengths

- Simple and widely used for monitoring SAD variability
- Capture the SST dipole pattern

Limitations

- Sensitive to box definitions (small shifts can change index values)
- SAODI partly overlaps with the Atlantic Niño region → may mix signals
- Indices do not separate atmosphere–ocean coupling mechanisms
- Cannot represent spatial shifts (e.g., latitudinal migration of SAD)

Monitoring: how do we define extreme SAD events?

- **Extreme SAD events**

Commonly defined when SAODI or SASDI exceed **± 1 standard deviation** from their climatological mean.

- **Public time series available**

Both indices (SAODI, SASDI) are openly provided by the **Teleconnection Index Online Tool** – **Federal University of Itajubá**

<https://app-indice.streamlit.app/>

(Drumond et al., 2025; in review).

How Does the SAD relate with South American Climate?

Relationship between SAD and the SAMS

(Bombardi & Carvalho, 2011)

- SAD associated with **dipole in rainfall** between **SE and NE Brazil**
- **Negative SAD** (cool NE pole x warm SW pole) – stronger SASH

SAMS (Bolivia-SE Brazil) wet season: earlier onset, longer & wetter

NE Brazil wet season: Later onset, shorter & drier

- **Positive SAD** (warm NE pole x cool SW pole) – weaker SASH

SAMS: later onset, shorter & drier

NE Brazil: earlier onset, longer & wetter

Fig. 4 Rank correlation between a the SAD index of October and Onset, b the SAD index of May and Demise, c the SAD index of April and accumulated precipitation, d the SAD index of April and Duration. Contour interval equal 0.1. *Solid lines* indicate positive values and *dashed lines* indicate negative values. *Shading* shows regions where the rank correlation is statistically significant at 5% level

Bombardi & Carvalho (2011)

- **Key process (Bombardi et al., 2014):** A Rossby wave train from the extratropical Pacific.

Negative SAD

- Cyclonic anomalies over SE Brazil
- Enhanced moisture transport from Amazon
- Intensification SACZ activity

Positive SAD

- Anticyclonic anomalies over SE Brazil
- Reduced moisture inflow from Amazon towards SE Brazil and weaker SACZ activity

a SLP & H500 (NEG)

b SLP & H500 (POS)

a Moisture Flux (NEG)

b Moisture Flux (POS)

Bombardi et al. (2014)

Methodological Sensitivity in Assessing SAD Impacts

Methodological choices may shape the SAD–precipitation relationships.

Example: SAODI - low skill in summer (weak N pole SST signal).

Analysis based on SAODI may present low impact during Summer.

Reboita et al. (2021): SAODI composites

— **Negative SAODI** → **wetter** northern SA during **winter and spring**

Carpenedo & da Silva (2022): linear correlations using SAODI

— **Except Summer:**

southern Cerrado: **Negative SAODI** → **wetter**; **positive SAODI** → **drier**.

Northern Brazil: **Negative SAODI** → **drier**; **positive SAODI** → **wetter**.

How Does the SAD Interact With Other Climate Modes?

SAD and Other Southern Hemisphere Dipoles

- SAD often occurs with other dipole patterns in SH: **SIOD** (South Indian Ocean Dipole) and **South Pacific dipole**, mainly in summer (*e.g. Venegas et al., 1997; Hermes & Reason, 2005; Yu et al., 2023*).
- These dipoles are influenced by large-scale atmospheric wave pattern in SH circulation known as the **zonal wavenumber-3/4**
- These wave patterns modify subtropical anticyclones, triggering the dipoles

Regression maps of the SST anomalies (C) on the summertime index of SAOD over 1979–1999.

Yu et al. (2023)

SAD and Other Climate Variability Modes

- Interaction with ENSO, AAO, AMO, and PDO on interannual to decadal timescales (Hermes & Reason 2005; Boschat et al. 2013; Morioka et al. 2014; Yu et al. 2022; Manta et al. 2024)

ENSO–SAD Interactions

- The strength of the connection depends on the timing and type of ENSO event – ENSO-SAD link is not stationary, it changes with time
- In austral summer, ENSO affects SAD mainly via the PSA wave train → modifies SASH (Morioka et al. 2014; Rodrigues et al. 2015)
- During El Niño (LN), positive (neg) SAD - stronger wet season SE Brazil
- Stronger in lagged **correlation, especially with Central Pacific El Niño events** (Rodrigues et al. 2015; Ham et al. 2021)
- Relationship is two-way: ENSO can lead SAD and SAD can also lead ENSO (e.g. Kayano et al. 2012; Bombardi & Carvalho 2011)

SAD and Other Climate Variability Modes

The ENSO-SAD relationship changes on decadal scales

- ENSO–SAD coupling strengthened in recent decades due to shifts in ENSO regimes and PDO/IPO/AMO phase reversals around the turn of the century (Kayano et al. 2012; Yu et al. 2017, 2024)
- Positive phase of Interdecadal Pacific Oscillation (IPO) favors negative SAD during El Niño on interdecadal scales (e.g. Bier, 2023)

AMO Influence on ENSO-SAD

- AMO also modulates ENSO regime: **warm AMO → more CP El Niño (stronger related with SAD)**; cold AMO → more EP El Niño (Wang et al. 2017).
- ENSO–SAD correlations stronger during warm AMO phase (2001–2020) and weaker during cold phase (1961–2000) (Yu et al. 2024)

How does the climate change affect the SAD?

- Climate Change is reorganizing the large-scale circulation
- CC affected the ENSO regime and teleconnections in the last decades, altering the ENSO–SAD relationship (Martín-Gomez et al. 2020)
- long-term changes in the SASH - SASH expansion during Summer influences a southward shift of SAD (Bier, 2023) and SACZ (Zilli et al., 2019)

Modeling the SAD in CMIP6

(Bier, 2023)

Historical period Performance

- CMIP6 models (FIO-ESM-2-0, CMCC-ESM2, CMCC-CM2-SR5) capture SAD features: spatial pattern, oscillation period, and seasonality.
- Fail to represent the **Atlantic Niño signal**, typically coupled to SAD.
- Do **not reproduce the southward shift** of SAD in recent decades.
- Implication: models may underestimate some air–sea coupling processes in the tropical South Atlantic.

Future Projections

- CMIP6 projects **stronger SST, MSLP, and precipitation anomalies**, especially under **SSP3-7.0**.
- SAD remains linked to a **dipole rainfall pattern** between northern and southeastern South America, with intensification of extreme events.

Modeling the SAD in CMIP6

(Nworgu et al., 2024)

- Models show **limited skill** in representing SAOD rainfall impacts over **SE Brazil during Austral Winter**
- **Divergent future projections** of SAOD–rainfall relationships under high-emission scenarios
- Highlights **large uncertainties** for countries affected by SAOD variability (South America + Africa)

Final Remarks

- SAD is associated with present-day South American climate: SACZ behavior, Amazon–SE Brazil moisture transport, and rainfall dipole between NEB and SE Brazil.
- Mechanisms involve SASH intensity/position changes; winds affect evaporation, surface heat fluxes, mixed-layer depth variability
- Rossby wave trains from the Pacific and wavenumber 3 or 4 pattern can also trigger changes in SASH.
- It shows seasonal variability (SASD in summer, SAOD in winter); and SAD is sensitive to index choice (SAODI vs SASDI).
- ENSO, AAO, AMO, PDO, and IPO modify SAD behavior on interannual–decadal timescales, producing non-stationary relationships.

Final Remarks

- Climate change: changes in ENSO regime and teleconnections; expansion of SASH that shifts SACZ and SAD southward
- CMIP6 models reproduce the SAD basic patterns but fail to capture some ocean–atmosphere coupling and show large uncertainty in future SAD–rainfall projections.
- Key open questions:
 - Long-term trends and mechanisms behind SAD seasonality
 - Changing ENSO–SAD link
 - Predictability and role of ocean–atmosphere coupling
 - Regional impacts in South America and Africa

Thank you!

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